

Creating an electronic database of terms used in the field of music and dance

Ochilova Mekhriniso Razokovna,
Senior teacher of ESP for Interfaculty department,
Bukhara State University
m.r.ochilova@buxdu.uz

Abstract. This article analyzes ways of creating online database and online dictionary in the specialization of music, art and dance. These analyses can be helpful for corpus linguistics and creation of online dictionaries.

Key words. Database, electronic dictionary, music and dance sphere, creation

Introduction. Over the years, attempts have been made to classify the main methods of formation of new terms. Summarizing the results of these studies, the following main methods can be distinguished:

1) semantic (using a word or phrase of a commonly used language as a term, giving it a new meaning). Compare:

advance in English - move forward in Uzbek,
retire in English - to retire in Uzbek.

The semantic method of term creation is the most common, moreover, such terms occupy the most important place in the terminology that is being formed to define the concepts of new fields of knowledge and areas of human activity.

2) morphological (creating a new term by means of affixation, combination). Compare:

danceable in English - danceable in Uzbek
dancegoer in English - participant in a dance course in Uzbek

3) syntactic (terminological phrases).

Compare:

dance hall in English - dance hall in Uzbek
dance card in English - dance card in Uzbek (the card with the names of the dancers)

4) words borrowed from other languages
Moulinet in French is "fast spin" in Uzbek.

Another way to create terms is to create abbreviations and special abbreviations, which have become more and more common recently

RLOD < reverse line dance, fig < figure, ftwk < footwork).

R.D. in the classification of dances. Batchelor identified four dance groups:

- dances imitating the movements of the fortress;
- circular dances performed by gradually bending the body forward and backward;
- dances in which performers sway back and forth;
- dances based on the movements of the first three groups"

Analysis. The American researcher R. Kraus paid attention to the composition of the participants, purpose, meaning and vocabulary of the dance in the classification of dances. Accordingly, he identified five dance groups: ballet; modern dance; social dance; stage dance; folk dance. L. Grove divides dances into 3 groups: figurative or poetic; descriptive; ritual, ceremonial. "Secret dances", "flowing dances", "magical dances" are being revived in modern psychological schools.

For these purposes, the spiritual experience of ritual dances, as well as its philosophical understanding in ancient texts, is studied and systematized.

Some researchers believe that terminological synonymy is completely unacceptable. Synonymous terms represent the same concepts, the same objects and phenomena of reality. V. P. Danilenko states that "it is characterized by the function of replacing term-synonyms". Examples of dance terminology: a) pirouette - pirouette (360 degree turn) is a term taken from the French language; pas de basque - on de basque (jumping from foot to foot, then stepping); b) hands across and back (English) - moulinet (French) (a cross is a figure of ancient dances: four dancers join the same hands and form a cross; d) terminological combination - abbreviation: diagonally to the center - DTC (from diagonal to center), Open Facing Position - OPF (open position), Line of Dance - LOD (dance line), Body Completes Turn - BCT (full turn).

In historical dance, balance is a dance movement with stepping from one foot to the other, lifting on half toes and bending the body. Balance (from the French word "equilibrium") and pas grave (from the French words "pas" "step", "grave" "heavy", "slow") were added to create the phrase balance minuet. A number of names that appeared in the Middle Ages entered the vocabulary of ballroom dancing for a long time. From them, it is possible to observe how actions have changed, how the same term served to denote different actions in different periods, and sometimes a certain similarity.

The word tour (from the French "tour" "to turn") used to mean a simple movement around the hall during marching dances, now it means turning the body 360 degrees around a vertical axis. In ballroom dancing, a tour means a forced movement around the hall:

- tour de mains (from the French "main" "hand") - turning, holding hands,
- tour sur place (from the French "place" "place") - turn on the spot,
- tour tape (from the French "tape" "slow") - a slow turn on one leg,
- tour en l'air (from the French "en l'air" "air") - a turn in the air (performed in a male dance).

Conclusion. The ambiguity of the terms does not allow them to be understood correctly. It is usually said that a term does not need context because it should be understood without context, but this rule cannot be absolute because, as with terminology, context is important. This is especially true for term categories, the so-called categorical ambiguity, the real way to overcome it is always to provide context in the literature or different places of these different terms in the classification system. In the creation of modern dictionaries, giving the rules of polysemy and determining the contextual meaning creates some difficulties, taking into account the fact that the process of uncertainty in terminology is very active, it is necessary to give the words in accordance with the rules of meeting lexical changes. The advantage of electronic dictionaries is that they can give multiple meanings of words. We can observe the presence of so-called "secondary uncertainty" terms in the dance terminology we are studying and analyze the possibilities of their presentation in dictionaries. Artificially introducing foreign terms into the language is not always justified. In such cases, it is necessary to use one's own language capabilities and to pay attention to maintaining the balance between the meaning of the term and the meaning of the term. Often terms that express certain concepts are not available in use. As a result, despite the fact that such concepts are extremely important and relevant, they are deprived of the possibility of wide spread. In the creation of the term, it is a lack of mutual systematicity with the essence of the concept it is supposed to represent.

References:

1. Даниленко В.П. Русская терминология: Опыт лингвистического описания. - М., 1977. – С.13.
2. Головин Б. Н. Лингвистические основы учения о терминах: Учебное пособие/Головин Б. Н., Кобрин Р. Ю. - М., 1987. – С.51.
3. Bahodirovna, A. M. “Semantic Field and Sema in Uzbek (In the Example of ‘Ma’naviyat’)”. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION, vol. 1, no. 4, Oct. 2022, pp. 77-80, <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJISE/article/view/173>.
4. Sumaira Nawaz, Khaitova Gulshan Bahodirovna, Akhmedova Mehrinigor Bahodirovna. “Explanation of Agricultural Terms in Dictionaries”.

Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies, Vol. 18, May 2022,
doi:10.21070/ijins.v18i.606.

5. ISLOMOV ELDOR YUSUPOVICH, AHMEDOVA MEHRINIGOR
BAHODIROVNA. THE ESSENCE OF SPIRITUALITY IN THE UZBEK
LANGUAGE. XIII МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ
КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ " ЯЗЫК И КУЛЬТУРА", Челябинск, 26 апреля 2018 года. -
P.12-15